

Manure: Production, Composition and Processing Techniques

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Introduction

Livestock waste is major source of -Greenhouse gas, Pathogens, Odour and 18 % of global methane is produced by livestock waste. Organic fertilizers (compost, vermicompost, vermiwash etc.), bioenergy (bio gas, electricity, biofuel, CNG etc.) make animal operations economically feasible and eco-friendly which ensures higher profit to livestock owners. Manure is a term is used for organic matter, mostly obtained from animal faeces including urine but, may also be used for organic matter obtained from human faeces, urine and agricultural leftover. Manures contribute to the fertility of the soil by adding organic matter and nutrients

Different Forms of Manure

1. **Liquid:** contain 4% or less solids
2. **Slurry:** 4 to 10% solids content
3. **Semi-Solid Manure:** 10 to 20% solids content
4. **Solid Manure:** >20% solids content

Chemical Compositions of Manure of Different Livestock Species

	Dairy Cattle	Beef Cattle	Ox	Pig	Chicken layers	Chicken broiler	Horse
Dry matter ash% of fresh manure	12.7	11.6	25	9.2	25.2	25.2	20.9
Organic material (%)	82.5	85	85	80	70	70	80
Total nitrogen (%)	3.9	4.9	4.5	7.5	5.4	6.8	2.9
Total phosphorus (%)	0.7	1.6	0.7	2.5	2.1	1.5	0.5
Total Potassium (%)	2.6	3.6	3.2	4.9	2.3	2.1	1.8
Biological oxygen demand	16.5	23	9	33	27	-	-
Chemical oxygen demand	88	95	11.8	95	90	-	-

Manure Processing Techniques

1. **Composting:** Composting is the rotting and conversion of organic waste into nutrient rich compost.
2. **Vermicomposting:** The process of worms and microorganisms to convert dead organic matter into nutrient rich humus. Organic matter cycles through the worm's digestive tract and is excreted as castings.

3. **Vermiwash:** Vermiwash is a liquid that is collected after the passage of water through a column of worm action. Contains excretory products, mucus secretion of earthworms with micronutrients from the soil organic molecules.

Anaerobic Fermentation (Biogas):

Anaerobic digestion, Biogas is generated

during anaerobic digestion when microorganisms break down (eat) organic materials in the absence of air (or oxygen). Biogas is mostly methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂), with very small amounts of water vapor and other gases.

Environmental Conditions of Biogas System: Temperature- 35 °C, pH- 7.2, Ratio of carbon to nitrogen- 25 to 30, Mixture Retention Time in the Digester Tank- retention time \propto gas production, Solids Concentration-7 to 9% of solids, Particle Size- Smaller the particle size, more the gas production (Rahi and Garshasbi, 2010).

Composition of Biogas (Rajati *et al.*, 2014)

Material	Percentage
Methane (CH ₄)	55% to 65%
Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂)	35% to 45%
Hydrogen Sulphide (H ₂ S)	0% to 3%
Hydrogen(H ₂)	0% to 1%
Oxygen (O ₂)	0% to 1%
Nitrogen (N ₂)	0% to 1%

Biogas Production Systems: There are two system of biogas production-

1. Biogas system with a floating lid (Indian model)
2. Biogas system with gas lid, a shared fermentation tank, and constant volume (Chinese model)
4. **Manure Cake:** Manure can be used for making manure cake, alternative to firewood in cooking. As a fuel in furnace.
5. **Solid Liquid Separator Technique:** Used to separate solid and liquid part of manure. Solid part can be used either in composting, vermicomposting or in anaerobic digestion to produce biogas, while liquid part used as fertilizer.

Figure 4: Manure Cake

Conclusions

Manure adds nutrients to the soil without affecting its fertility. It does not damage crops and produces healthy plants; ultimately decreased public health risk. Proper production and utilization of livestock manure can enhance soil biological activity, favoring nutrient cycling and availability for crops and generating the “glue” critical to stable soil aggregates. Several studies demonstrated the positive effects of manure on soil biological properties, and its impact in microbes and larger fauna. It provides effective solution for pollution caused by livestock waste and also provides renewable and cheap energy source.

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